

Realizing Symmetry-Breaking Architectures in Soap Films

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Abstract: We show here that soap films – typically expected to host symmetric molecular arrangements – can be constructed with differing opposite surfaces, breaking their symmetry, and making them reminiscent of functional biological motifs found in Nature. Using fluorescent molecular probes as dopants on different sides of the film, resonance energy transfer could be employed to confirm the lack of symmetry, which was found to persist on timescales of several minutes. Further, a theoretical analysis of the main transport phenomena involved yielded good agreement with the experimental observations.

Main: Long ago, Hermann Weyl expressed the sentiment: “All *a priori* statements in physics find their origin in symmetry” [1]. Indeed, our very existence is a byproduct of broken symmetries at the subatomic level [2], even as the laws which govern us are engendered in conservation thereof [3,4]. Nature makes a compelling case for symmetry-breaking constructs to realize function: asymmetric inside-outside arrangement of membrane-bound proteins on a thylakoid membrane enables the utilization of proton gradients to drive life-sustaining reactions such as synthesis of ATP. More generally, symmetry-breaking arrangements of phospholipids lead to transmembrane electric and chemical potential gradients, resulting in different propensity for interaction with substances on the opposite sides [5,6], thus driving biological function. The retinal distribution of rods and cones is also radially asymmetric, yet another well-known example of a mesoscopic symmetry-breaking supramolecular arrangement extant in nature [7,8].

Soap films and bubbles have intrigued children and brilliant minds alike for centuries [9–11]; they poetically straddle the interface of art [12] and science, with interests spanning from their interference fringes to their rupture behavior and longevity [13,14]. These inconspicuous dynamical fluid structures bear a resemblance to aforementioned biological membranes – not in the least when it comes to beauty and complexity. Considered as thin layers of liquid stabilized by amphiphilic surfactant molecules [15], soap films bear topological resemblance to natural lipid bilayers enclosing an aqueous phase, *e.g.* thylakoids. Concurrently, the so-generated air-water interfaces also likens them to cell walls.

From this perspective, the possibility of generating a symmetry-breaking architecture on opposite interfaces of otherwise intrinsically symmetric soap films is an intriguing proposition. If realized, it would bring soap films closer to natural membranes, and open possibilities for novel functions. Furthermore, the aqueous and surfactant phases that comprise soap films can be tuned by dopants influencing their properties; see *e.g.* recent reports on how surfactants may control the strength of the strong electric field at the gas-water dielectric interface [16], potentially leading to ultrafast reactions compared to homogenous bulk conditions [17]. Other potential applications can be envisioned in the context of gas permeation through soap films, where surfactants can fine-tune different permeability values at the two interfaces [18] and a recently proposed concept of photosynthetic soft membranes [19]. These favorable prospects taken together with their low cost, easy generation, and scalability, could make soap films with

mesoscopic tailored supramolecular arrangements – much as proteins are preferentially arranged in lipid bilayers – robust building blocks for future applications.

In this report, we present therefore, to the best of our knowledge, first proof of a symmetry-breaking supramolecular arrangement in soap films on the mesoscopic scale, by employing amphiphilic fluorescent molecular probes as dopants, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. *Left:* Molecular structures of amphiphilic Fluorescein (blue), Rhodamine (red), and different base surfactants (black) used in this study, together with a schematic depiction of the setup used for measurements and a cartoon depiction of the envisioned symmetry-breaking soap film. *Right:* Schematic depiction of the experiments used in this work to distinguish a symmetric and symmetry-breaking soap film.

The molecules chosen were surface-active analogues of Fluorescein and Rhodamine, a classic donor-acceptor pair with significant spectral overlap to undergo Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET). Upon confining the dyes in micelles of the non-ionic surfactant $C_{12}E_6$ (hexaethylene glycol monododecyl ether) with a hydrodynamic radius ~ 3.7 nm [20], efficient ($>80\%$) energy transfer could be observed at an average occupancy of ~ 1 /micelle of each dye. This was found consistent with a Förster radius (corresponding to 50% efficiency of energy transfer) of approximately 5.5 nm for related Fluorescein-Rhodamine couples [21], thus validating the choice of dopants.

Well-established as a “molecular ruler” [22], FRET is very sensitive to the distance between donor and acceptor, with efficiency falling off as the sixth power of the distance. Occurrence of FRET, therefore, is typically limited to donor-acceptor distances <8 nm. Soap films, during the experiments, had thicknesses exceeding 500 nm, which could be independently verified using both film rupture velocity measurements and non-observation of interference colors. A set of FRET experiments, as illustrated in the right panel of Figure 1, can therefore be rationalized to test the symmetry-breaking hypothesis in such films. Doping the donor and acceptor on different sides of the soap film should preclude FRET, presenting direct evidence of symmetry-breaking on the measured timescales. Conversely, FRET can be expected to occur

in a facile way if the dopants migrate between the different interfaces *or* if they are deliberately doped on the same side (control).

Given the flexible and dynamical nature of the fluid thin film, conventional doping methods such as drop-casting or injection with a syringe tip proved ineffective. Large turbulence generated in the mesoscopic film due to the impinging drop was found sufficient to trivially mix the dyes. Consequently, the donor, Fluorescein, and acceptor, Rhodamine, were doped on either different or same sides of a soap film by employing a Rayleigh spray nozzle (Figure S20). This enabled the generation an aerosol of the dye solution (10 μM of the dye at different concentrations of the base surfactant, with the latter typically at one or ten times the critical micellar concentration (CMC)). The mean droplet size was *ca.* 20 μm , and deposition occurred on the same or different sides of the soap film. In all cases, the soap film was made from the same base surfactant concentration as used for the dye solution. This method allowed for introduction of the dopants with negligible **mechanical** perturbation of the soap film membrane, **as only small surface energy changes can be expected due to coalescence of droplets with sizes up to approximately 100 μm with the film (*vide infra*)**. The three base surfactants tested were C_{12}E_6 , sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC), presenting cases of a neutral, anionic and cationic surfactant, respectively.

The method of using FRET to detect migration of dyes from one side to the other side of the film could be validated via the control (Figure 2, first column) where 10 μM solutions of the donor and acceptor were sprayed on the same side of the film. Energy transfer could be readily confirmed between them by direct observation of the acceptor's spectral band at 590 nm while exclusively exciting the donor at 470 nm.

Figure 2. Steady state luminescence data recorded for the amphiphilic dyes ($10 \mu\text{M}$ solutions in the base surfactant) spray-doped on soap films of CTAC (top panel) and SDS (bottom panel) made from the same base surfactant. Excitation wavelength was 470 nm where the donor Fluorescein was predominantly excited. *Top left:* Fluorescein and Rhodamine sprayed on the same side of the soap film (base surfactant CTAC; concentration = 1.1 mM , 1 CMC). Immediate appearance of the Rhodamine acceptor fluorescence peak at 590 nm clearly indicates the occurrence of FRET in the control, validating the method. *Top middle:* Fluorescein and Rhodamine sprayed on different sides of the soap film (base surfactant CTAC, 1 CMC). Only Fluorescein fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{max}} \approx 535 \text{ nm}$) is observed; absence of any acceptor peak indicates persistent broken symmetry for at least 13 minutes, when the film broke. *Top right:* Fluorescein and Rhodamine sprayed on different sides of the soap film (base surfactant CTAC; concentration = 11 mM , 10 CMC). *Bottom panel:* Same as the top panel, but with base surfactant SDS. *Note:* Signals in SDS are an order of magnitude lower than CTAC; the Fluorescein signal therefore nearly coincided with the background and has been plotted as a blue shaded line after correcting the data for background. SDS data at 10 CMC has been normalized to the fibre background at 540 nm for clearer depiction of the acceptor intensity increment.

Upon spraying $10 \mu\text{M}$ solutions of the donor and acceptor on different sides of the soap film and excitation of the donor at 470 nm , persistent symmetry-breaking on the timescale of at least several minutes could be observed for base surfactants CTAC and SDS (Figure 2, middle column, top and bottom; concentration of CTAC = 1.1 mM , and SDS = 8 mM , i.e. 1 CMC), as evidenced by the sole presence of the donor peak (centred at *ca.* 535 nm) and absence of any acceptor peak (expected at 590 nm) in the fluorescence spectra. For the case of base surfactant C_{12}E_6 , however, no symmetry-breaking could be observed at any concentration, see Figure S4. Finally, upon spraying the dopants on different sides of the film, only partial symmetry-breaking could be observed in CTAC and SDS when their concentration was ten times the CMC (Figure 2, last column).

Taken together, the data – qualitatively similar for both surfactants SDS and CTAC – establish symmetry-breaking on the timescale of several minutes when the base surfactant concentration is 1 CMC, limited only by the stability of the soap film itself. Meanwhile, the non-observance of symmetry-breaking in the experiments conducted at 10 CMC is also amenable to a simple explanation: micellar solubilization is likely responsible for transport of the dopants across the aqueous phase, and symmetrizes the interfaces. This interpretation is justified by the fact that the majority of dyes can be expected to be present in base surfactant micelles and not as monomers at the interface, in 10 CMC of the base surfactant. A distinct time evolution is also observed in the spectra at 10 CMC for SDS (Figure 2, bottom right), which we tentatively attribute to a combined effect of micelle-assisted dopant transport and dye de-aggregation.

Time-resolved lifetime measurements reveal that dynamic quenching is insignificant in the control when Fluorescein and Rhodamine are sprayed on the same side of the film (Figure S12), consistent with the *ca.* 4 ns lifetime of the donor, during which the extent of diffusion is expected to be minimal. The largely static quenching (quenching sphere of action) is manifest in the lifetime decay becoming biexponential [23]. Estimates of the extent of dye loading per spray **using absorption measurements** suggest nearly complete geometric surface coverage by the dopants: therefore, the relatively smaller extent of observed quenching (~5%) points to the presence of molecular aggregates and interactions between them. This notion is corroborated by the observation of increased self-quenching instead of energy transfer upon substantial increase of the acceptor loading, and an overall lowering of the signal intensity (Figure S8).

We observe that timescales for the emission intensity increase at the single interface are found to be consistent with the slowest processes associated with the envisioned main transport phenomena illustrated in Figure 3. Here, the overall doping process can be thought to be characterized by four critical steps: A) the deposition of the spray droplet on the soap film, B) micelle and/or monomer diffusion to the contact area of the droplet and soap film, C) Diffusion of the dopant within the micelle and subsequent overcoming of the Gibbs free energy barrier for deposition on the soap film surface, and finally, D) mixing of the dopant molecule at the interface under the effect of Marangoni flows. As detailed in SI, when using surfactant of the same nature for both the doping solution and the film, upon the spray, self-standing droplets can be envisioned in the vicinity of monolayers. Under such an assumption, the slowest transport phenomena can be associated with the first three steps and estimated in the order of

minute timescales, while the last process involving mixing of the monomers on the interface after deposition may take seconds or shorter.

Figure 3. A multiscale pictorial representation of the main transport phenomena that are considered to be responsible for the soap film doping process. **A:** A nozzle, at a distance h from a soap film monolayer, atomizes the doping solution thus generating droplets with a given size distribution. **B:** Assuming that the base surfactant solution is at a concentration exceeding CMC, a single droplet (generic diameter D_d) deposited on a soap film monolayer carries a number of micelles (generic diameter δ) formed by surfactant molecules (monomers). Deposited droplets can either stand or coalesce with the soap film monolayer. **C:** Micelles reach the soap film and deposit single monomers of the doping molecule that are **D:** spread all over the monolayer under the action of Marangoni forces.

Micellar solubilization was found to be a key factor controlling the symmetry-breaking, thus necessitating use of CMC or sub-CMC concentrations of the base surfactants. The use of such concentrations was not sufficient however, as was found for the case of $C_{12}E_6$, where no-symmetry breaking was observed even at 1 CMC. This highlights that both the nature and concentration of base surfactant are important.

Broadly, both molecular and mechanical aspects can be considered to furnish explanations for the observed phenomena. For the latter, the doping methodology and droplet size assume critical importance. A mechanically “non-perturbative” condition may be discussed in a thermodynamic perspective, using the ratio between the induced free energy change associated with the droplet coalescence process and the initial free energy of the soap film before coalescence. This dimensionless quantity is presented in Figure 4 for our system, with analytical expressions detailed in the SI. The black curve shows that, up to around $100 \mu\text{m}$ droplet diameter, the induced free energy change is very small compared to that of the soap film, whereas it steps-up quickly for larger droplets and eventually becomes comparable for mm-sized droplets. Accordingly, we have observed that the dissymmetry is destroyed upon use of such macro-droplets for doping, thus associating the non-perturbative condition with the minimal free energy change induced by the fine spray. We note this analysis is for a single coalescence event, while doping may involve several such events. The non-perturbative conditions with the adopted spray could then be sought in the time lag among concurrent coalescence events, which may be sufficient to minimize the cumulative free energy step in the system.

Figure 4. Dimensionless free energy change in the soap film induced by the droplet coalescence process as a function of the droplet diameter. The gray transparent region shows the droplet diameter range tested with the adopted spraying technique where symmetry breaking has been observed.

From the molecular perspective, it is notable that there is an order of magnitude difference between the CMCs of the base surfactants: a few mM for SDS and CTAC, and *ca.* 80 μM for C_{12}E_6 . The value for C_{12}E_6 can be expected to be closer to that of the dopants, potentially resulting in competition for surface occupancy – a well-known possibility for mixed surfactant systems [24] – and solubilization of the dopant dyes also at 1 CMC. The contrast is also found when considering physical properties: CTAC and SDS are charged as opposed to the neutral C_{12}E_6 , and the resulting electrostatic interactions can be expected to contribute to both the droplet-deposition and coalescence dynamics, as well as the extent of dopant aggregation (*vide supra*). Indeed, it could be confirmed that symmetry could not be broken if dopant solutions in CTAC were sprayed on a soap film made of SDS, even at 1 CMC, owing to the opposite charges.

We also note that signal intensities in CTAC exceed those in SDS and C_{12}E_6 by an order of magnitude. The spectral and time-resolved observations are consistent with the cationic surfactant both assisting in breaking up aggregates and stabilizing the anionic species of Fluorescein, which is known to have almost thrice the quantum yield of the neutral molecule (with the latter being the dominant species in SDS and C_{12}E_6) [25,26]. Collectively, the observations carry a two-fold message. First, not only is judicious choice of base surfactant and its concentration necessary for symmetry-breaking, it also offers an opportunity to tune the photophysical characteristics of the dopants. Second, there is room for synergizing favorable photophysical effects (*e.g.* less aggregation) together with other properties specific to the

mixed-surfactant interface (*e.g.* surface competition preventing symmetry-breaking, or effects on film stability).

To conclude, we have demonstrated the construction of a mesoscopic symmetry-breaking supramolecular arrangement on soap films, on timescales substantially long enough to allow for meaningful chemistry to take place. Further, we have experimentally delineated critical factors enabling the symmetry-breaking: optimal base surfactant and concentrations for film preparation, and a mechanically non-perturbative and scalable spray technique for film doping. Using a multiscale model of the critical transport phenomena, insight was gained into the dynamics. Droplet deposition, coalescence, and dye deaggregation could be isolated as rate-limiting steps; a free-energy change calculation for the coalescence process in particular allowed for quantitative estimates of permissible droplet-sizes for symmetry-breaking, highlighting the importance of the doping methodology. Finally, the evaluated timescales of these processes – on the order of several minutes – were found in good agreement with observations, validating the proposed model. Inasmuch as all calculations in the latter have been undertaken with robust estimates of the physical parameters from the literature, the results can be regarded as general.

Langmuir-Blodgett-Kuhn (LBK) monolayers [27] present earlier attempts to construct supramolecular assemblies at the air-water interface. They embody critical handicaps compared to the natural membranes that inspired them, however, being rigid and inflexible, and suffering from stability issues that have limited the possibilities for scalability [28]. This work is suggestive of the use of soap films as viable alternatives, which can potentially overcome the bottlenecks encountered in LBK monolayers that precluded their widespread application. Soap films offer a unique range of compositional tunability, self-assembly, transport and interfacial properties, *and* scalability in form of 3D-soap foams or bubble-pair interfaces. They are fluid, dynamical mesoscopic structures capable of accommodating flexible supramolecular arrangements, making them more faithful representatives of their natural counterparts. Therefore, the fundamental finding of generating a symmetry-breaking arrangement in soap films can present a first step towards potential future applications, *e.g.* molecular sensors, chemically or optically triggered switches, opto-electronic devices, or asymmetrically arranged catalysts for solar energy conversion. It also suggests the possibility of using soap films as platforms for better understanding the structure and function of natural membranes.

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Author contributions:

H.S. and N.K. carried out spectroscopic measurements, data analysis, and visualization. L.H. conceptualized and guided the experiments. A.A. performed the synthesis and its validation. E.C. conceptualized the modelling activities, G.F. and L.B. executed all modelling and computational work, validation, and data visualization. I.S. and E.C. conceived the doping methodology. C.R. provided the spray nozzle and its characterization. S.B. and A.A. contributed to the methodology. I.S. conceived the idea and found financial support. L.H., E.C., S.B. supervised all research activities and found financial support. All authors contributed to data interpretation and result presentation. N.K. wrote the manuscript with critical contribution from all co-authors.

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Data and materials availability: All data are available in the main text or the supplementary materials. Correspondence and any requests for materials should be addressed to L.H.

Supplementary Materials

Materials and Methods

Supplementary Text

Figs. S1 to S24

Tables S1 to S2

Equations S1 to S19

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